

Integration	Complete adaptation to a foreign culture, which begins to feel like one's own. Formation of a multicultural personality.	Playing situations from the point of view of different cultures and analyzing the choice of this behavioral strategy. <i>Purpose:</i> interpretation of cultural differences, formation of the skill of switching from one behavioral model to another.
Contextual assessment	Analysis and assessment of the situation of the possibility of cultural behavior options (to act in Japanese or in Russian).	
Constructive marginality	The personality is outside the cultural framework, there is no natural cultural identity, there is no absolutely correct behavior.	

Thus, intercultural communicative competence is an important professional component of a modern specialist, the basis which are laid during training in higher educational institutions. An important task of modern higher institutions is to create favorable conditions for the formation of intercultural communicative competence of future specialists and the use of modern computer information technologies in full.

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FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT AS AN EFFECTIVE WAY OF ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract

Today, the traditional education system cannot meet the demands of a volatile society, which eventually becomes unstable. Although they have academic knowledge, students often cannot apply their knowledge in a changing life. In accordance with this, the modern education system needs to introduce new approaches in the system of assessing students' educational achievements, in the formation of their general educational competencies. The use of one of such new approaches in the assessment of students' academic achievements- formative assessment increases students' motivation to study, develops skills of academic independence, influences the formation of personality who will be able to compete and work in his/ her future international labor market meeting all the requirements of modern society.

Keywords: criteria- based assessment, formative assessment, students' achievement, assessment for learning, foreign language

Nowadays in connection with modern tendencies in the development of education system of the world evaluation of students' activities has become an important element of the pedagogical process, and evaluation is a powerful pedagogical tool that performs a particular task of the teacher. Any evaluation activity is based on the student's or teacher's need to get information about how effectively their interaction takes place during the educational process.

The assessment system is an effective tool not only for measuring student achievement in foreign language teaching process, but also for improving the quality of education. Therefore, the evaluation system is understood not only as the scale that is used when setting marks, but, above all, the mechanism itself for the implementation of diagnostic and developmental

activities of the teacher and student as full participants in the educational process. Assessment is also a reflection of the process of interaction between the state and the school, teacher and student, school and parents.

Assessment and teaching process are interrelated processes. There are three interdependent types of assessment: diagnostic, formative and summative. The teacher will not be able to apply formative assessment at the proper level without the results of the diagnostic assessment. And the quality of formative assessment in the lesson will affect the results of summative assessment. By maintaining this consistency in the assessment, teachers can achieve a high level of learning.

The concept of "assessment for learning" gained its fame in 1999 after the publication of a brochure with the same name, the author of which was the Assessment

Reform Group from among the academies of Great Britain, working together since 1989, in order to prepare evidence materials to inform teachers and developers of methods. [1]

The work of this group was based on the works of P. Black and D. William, who noted that the improvement of learning depends on five key conditions such as effective feedback from teachers to students, active involvement of students in the process of their own teaching, taking into account in teaching the results obtained during the assessment, understanding how the motivation and self-esteem of students depends on the assessment, and students' ability to self-evaluate.

The assessment for learning approach is in the focus of solving the problem of improving the teaching and learning processes. The most appropriate mechanism for the requirements of modern society, which takes into account the individual abilities of students and their age characteristics, is formative assessment, which is also called assessment for learning. Assessment for learning is a process of searching and interpreting data used by students and their teachers to determine the stage at which students are in the process of their learning, the direction in which they should develop, and how best to achieve the required level (Group Assessment Reforms, 2002).

Formative assessment is not a tool or a case, but a set of methods with a common feature: they all lead to some kind of action that improves learning for Black and William, as well as many other experts in this field. [2]

In general, research shows that formative assessment is not an instrument that is formative; it is the use of information collected by any means to adapt education and training, which has a "formative" advantage.

The purpose using formative assessment in foreign language teaching is to adjust the activities of teachers and students in the learning process. Activity adjustment involves setting tasks by the teacher or together with students to improve learning outcomes. Formative assessment enables the teacher to track the process of students' progress towards the goals of their teaching and helps the teacher to adjust the learning process at an early stage, and the student to realize a greater degree of responsibility for their education. At the same time, it should be noted that formative assessment is not a new phenomenon in education. The current assessment performed part of the function of formative assessment, but this assessment often turned into an end in itself and was realized at the level of only fixing knowledge-ignorance, skill-inability and the so-called accumulation of marks in the journal. Thus, formative (current) assessment is understood as determining the current level of knowledge and skills acquisition in the process of daily work in the classroom and/or at home, the implementation of the operational relationship between the student and the teacher in the learning process. It allows students to understand how well they perform tasks during the study of new material and achieve learning goals and objectives.

Formative assessment is used in everyday practice (every hour, daily). With this type of assessment, there must be a direct communication that ensures progress

in learning. Formative assessment helps the teacher to track progress in the classroom. Thus, it has formative, stimulating and motivating functions for students to learn foreign language by self-effort, and self-education. If we imagine that children are flowers, then summative evaluation of plants is simply their measurement. It may be interesting to compare and analyze the measurement results, but this does not affect plant growth in any way. Formative assessment is equivalent to caring for a plant and watering it according to the needs of plants, which directly affects their growth.

The process of formative assessment is a cyclical structure illustrating that assessment acts as a continuous process integrated with the methodology of teaching and learning aimed at eliminating gaps in students' knowledge. [3] When one gap is eliminated, another opens up in the course of advancing to the next stage of learning, and formative assessment is designed to eliminate such gaps in learning again and again.

The formative assessment process begins with teachers defining the learning goals for a specific lesson or sequence of lessons and determining the criteria for their success. Successful criteria determine compliance with the purpose of teaching and are used as the means of control and verification in teaching. Before the beginning of the lesson, these goals and success criteria should be agreed with the students.

The next step of formative assessment is the identifying evidence of learning. The key point in identifying evidence of learning, regardless of the methods and techniques used, is that all information can help in the development of teaching methods. According to the results of the assessment, the teacher can adjust the teaching methods. Interpretation of evidence is the next key step that should be discussed. As a result of formative assessment, teachers determine the educational achievements of students and analyze them, determining the level of what students have understood, what their misconceptions are, what knowledge they have or do not have, and what skills they have or lack. While the interpretation of the evidence is being carried out, teachers may not realize enough evidence to explain the reasons for the student's academic achievements. In particular, when implementing a pair assessment, students can interpret the learning outcomes themselves in accordance with the criteria of learning success.

Identifying learning gaps is also one of the important steps in the process of formative assessment in our foreign language teaching process. The purpose of formative assessment is to eliminate gaps between the student's current achievements and learning goals. Interpretation of the proofs of the results of formative assessment is the key to determining the relationship between the present status of students' learning and learning goals. The elimination of gaps is achieved by providing feedback on the degree of assimilation of educational material.

The next essential part of the structure of formative assessment process is feedback. To be effective in promoting learning, feedback is needed to help students achieve high learning outcomes. Within the framework of formative assessment, teachers contribute descrip-

tive feedback for students regarding the successful criterion and the progress of students in order to eliminate knowledge gaps. Some experts believe that whatever resources would not be involved in feedback, they should answer three main questions for students such as "Where am I going in my studies? (what are the learning goals?)", "How am I progressing in my studies? (what progress has been made towards achieving the goal?)", "What should I learn in the future? (what kind of activity is necessary to achieve the best learning outcome?)". [4] Thus, feedback should be used to improve the learning process.

Adaptation/ responsibility for learning needs. As a result of feedback, teachers plan activities to meet the needs of students. By engaging in self-assessment, students, they also adjust their own learning by choosing appropriate methods and strategies of teaching and learning.

Scaffolding of new learning. According to Vygotsky, the term "scaffolding" characterizes the support in the learning process that teachers give to students during teaching in order to move into the "zone of immediate development" from what they already know to what they can do in the future and eliminate the gap between their present learning and learning goals. The teacher helps them by giving the necessary instructions for teaching in such a way that they master complex material, eliminating gaps in learning themselves. Formative assessment is implemented through scaffolding to determine the degree of effectiveness of the student and, accordingly, the necessary adjustment of the teaching methodology is carried out.

The final step in the process of formative assessment is to eliminate the gaps between where the student is currently and what he wants to achieve in the course of learning in the future. As soon as one gap is eliminated, the teacher chooses new learning goals and new gaps are created, thereby updating the cycle of formative assessment. [5]

The holistic process of formative assessment depends on the culture of the classroom, where students feel safe and comfortable to implement constructive feedback from students. To ensure such a psychological and pedagogical favorable climate, teachers must approve the culture of the class, taking into account the individual and age characteristics of students.

Despite of the structure of formative assessment process, it is worth to note the main principles of formative assessment that teachers in their activities should be guided. The main principles of formative assessment include significance that can be described as the focus on evaluating the most significant learning outcomes and student activities, adequacy (tracking the compliance of the assessment of knowledge, skills, values, competencies with the goals and results of training), objectivity and fairness (implementation of thorough development of specific evaluation criteria), and integration (the implementation of assessment as a planned and carefully thought-out part of the learning process). [6] Openness also plays an essential role in formative assessment of students' achievements in teaching process. It can be described as informing students of assessment criteria and methods in advance, before doing

the work. Students can participate in the development of evaluation criteria. The next principle is the availability. It is striving for simplicity and clarity of forms, methods, goals and the evaluation process for all participants of the educational process. Formative assessment should be systematic and benevolence (creating conditions for a partnership between a teacher and a student, stimulating the growth of achievements, aimed at the development and support of students). Every teacher who follows these simple principles of formative assessment in their lessons can achieve academic success in their teaching process.

All types of assessment, and formative assessment in particular, involve the use of carefully developed criteria for organizing the evaluation of students' work. Evaluation using criteria makes this process transparent and understandable for all participants of the educational process. Criteria contribute to the objectification of evaluation. The basis for the development of criteria for assessing students' academic achievements are educational goals. The criteria can be prepared by a teacher or with the participation of students. The joint development of criteria (teacher – student) allows students to form a positive attitude to assessment and increase their responsibility for achieving the result. When developing evaluation criteria, it is important to always keep in mind the objectives and content of the lesson. The criteria developed for the evaluation of intermediate works (formative evaluation) should describe and evaluate only what is stated in the goal.

The content of the criteria should be understandable to students and parents, it should be written in a clear and accessible language. The evaluation criteria should be brought to the attention of students (placed on stands, on the blackboard, in the students' workbook). Criteria help students to evaluate the quality of their own work more objectively. The ability to evaluate based on criteria remains with a person for life. The teacher should not forget that it is necessary to acquaint students with the evaluation criteria before completing the task.

Effectively developed evaluation criteria and their gradation clearly demonstrate to students what and how will be evaluated, and also serve as a good guide for students in the process of doing work. Gradation of criteria is a description of different levels of achievement of the expected result. According to researchers the more specific the evaluation criteria are presented, the better the student will understand what he needs to do to successfully complete the tasks.

All in all, there are many reasons for the assessment of academic achievements of learners in foreign language teaching process. One of them is achieving greater responsibility of students- ensuring the development of students' self-esteem, ensuring a continuous link between teaching a foreign language and its effectiveness. Thus, it can be concluded that academic achievements are determined in the scope of the totality of knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of language activity, which students have the opportunity to independently evaluate.

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